

**Combating gender stereotypes by
highlighting women's contribution to
the history of societies**

Reference: 101087984

Co-funded by
the European Union

National Report

Athens, Greece

WP2 D2.1

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Amendment History

Version	Revision	Date	Author	Modification
1	0	11/09/2023	Dimitra Sofianou	First version
1	1	28/09/2023	Dimitra Sofianou	Reviewed version
2	0	29/09/2023	Dimitra Sofianou	Final version
2	1	04/12/2023	Dimitra Sofianou	Final version

1. GENDER EQUALITY AND GENDER REPRESENTATION IN GREECE	
1.1	STRUCTURAL CONSTRAINTS IN RELATION TO GENDER EQUALITY 4
1.2	GENDER REPRESENTATION IN HISTORY OF GREECE 5
1.3	GENDER REPRESENTATION IN HISTORY OF ATHENS 6
2. FEMALE FOOTPRINT IN ATHENS	
2.1	SAPPHO, THE LYRIC POET 7
2.2	MANTO MAVROGENOUS, THE GREEK HEROINE OF THE 1821 7
2.3	KATINA PAXINOY, THE FIRST NON-AMERICAN WOMAN WINNING AN OSCAR 7
2.4	ANTIGONI METAXA-KRONTIRA, THE CREATOR OF GREEK CHILDREN’S THEATRE..... 8
2.5	OPI ZOUNI, A FEMALE GREEK ARTIST 8
2.6	ROZA IMVRIOTI, THE PIONEER TEACHER 8
2.7	LELA KARAGIANNI, THE FIRST GREEK FIGHTER AGAINST SECOND WORLD WAR 8
2.8	KALLIROI PAREN, THE FIRST GREEK FEMINIST 9
2.9	MELINA MERCOURI, THE GREEK AMBASSADOR 9
2.10	TZENI KAREZI, A TALENTED ACTRESS 9
3. CITY’S PRACTICES AND LOCAL STRATEGIES IN DISSEMINATING HISTORY PATTERNS.
4. FIRST FOCUS GROUP WITH YOUNG PEOPLE: ANALYSES AND RESULTS.....	10
4.1.	‘RELEVANCE WITH THE FIELD OF HISTORY’ 11
4.2.	‘LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE IN HISTORY’ 11
4.3.	‘METHODS TO PROMOTE WOMEN’S FOOTPRINT IN HISTORY’ 12
5. SECOND FOCUS GROUP WITH YOUNG PEOPLE: ANALYSES AND RESULTS 	13
5.1.	‘RELEVANCE WITH THE FIELD OF HISTORY’ 14
5.2.	‘LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE IN HISTORY’ 14
5.3.	METHODS TO PROMOTE WOMEN’S FOOTPRINT IN HISTORY’ 15
6. FOCUS GROUP WITH STAKEHOLDERS: ANALYSES AND RESULTS 	16
6.1.	‘RELEVANCE WITH THE FIELD OF HISTORY’ 16
6.2.	‘HISTORY THROUGH THE LENS OF THEIR EXPERTISE’ 16
6.3.	‘EXPERIENCE WITH YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE FIELD OF HISTORY’ 17
6.4.	‘WOMEN’S FOOTPRINT IN HISTORY’ 17
6.5.	SUGGESTIONS FROM PARTICIPANTS ON FEMALE FOOTPRINT IN THE CITY/IN HISTORY. 18
6. CONCLUSIONS.....	16

1. Gender equality and gender representation in Greece

1.1 Structural constraints in relation to gender equality

The current structural constraints regarding gender equality in Greece are highly associated to the ideological commitment of Greeks to the institution of the family, which is very high by EU standards, but also to the social effects of the economic crisis of 2009 that Greece is still dealing with its consequences.

In Greece, the concept of family is traditionally understood in a broader context that encompasses kinship ties and plays a central role in providing care and support. Within this framework, the family is responsible for various forms of caregiving, including childcare, care for adults, accommodation, and emotional support. Since the 1980s, Greece has undergone significant changes in terms of gender roles and the structure of the family, due to migration to urban centers. As people moved away from their extended family networks in rural areas, the pattern of the nuclear family became more prevalent. This shift from extended to nuclear family structures brought about changes in family dynamics and a greater emphasis on individual needs, aspirations, and autonomy within the family context. These changes were marked by feminist movements that led to law reforms, such as the Family Law reform of 1983, which included a lot of the claims of women's associations (Papadopoulos, 1998. Davaki, 2001).

Despite all these shifts and the steps toward gender equality, it seems that traditional family values continue to be important for many Greeks. The concept of family still extends beyond the nuclear unit to include extended family members and close kin. Greek families tend to have strong bonds and maintain close relationships, with a focus on mutual support, care, and collective well-being. This fact impacts gender equality and the sustainment of traditional gender roles. Thus, women may take on more domestic and caregiving responsibilities while men focus on work and providing for the family. However, there is an increasing trend towards more egalitarian gender roles, with shared household tasks and childcare responsibilities.

The gender wage gap in Greece has been a persistent issue, as highlighted by various studies and data. The ratio of female to male earnings had declined from about 35% in the 1970s to roughly 25-30% in the 1990s. Nevertheless, the pay gap between women and men in Greece in 2010 was still 22% (European Commission, 2012).

Historically, women have been underrepresented in various sectors of Greek society, including politics, corporate leadership, and certain professions. In terms of politics, Greece had made some progress in increasing the representation of women in the parliament and government. In the 2019 legislative election, a record number of women were elected to the Hellenic Parliament, accounting for about 18% of the seats. This was a significant improvement compared to previous years, but it still indicated that women were not yet equally represented.

Balancing work and family responsibilities remains a challenge for many Greek women. Juggling professional aspirations with household duties and caregiving can be demanding. However, there is a growing recognition of the importance of work-life balance, and discussions around policies to support women in managing these responsibilities are gaining attention.

The financial crisis and the economic downturn that Greece faced from 2009 until 2016, led to a broad deregulation of employment, including the relaxation of collective agreements and enforced reduction in the minimum wage, severe cuts in pensions, as well as benefits and subsidies. All these changes affected primarily women, according to the unemployment records of 2013. Nevertheless, part-time work is not fully included in the statistical data since a substantial part of it is hidden within the dark area of the flourishing informal economy. Many women do not appear in the official statistics, as they are either paid cash in hand or do piece work or are unofficially employed in family enterprises (Nikolakopoulou-Stefanou, 1994).

Furthermore, austerity has also intensified issues of discrimination against women in the labour market. Stereotyping seems to be well-grounded in a number of male-dominated sectors (e.g. police, the army), but also in the education, public administration and health services sectors and has been impeding promotion and professional development of women disproportionately. It has become quite common that young women are often asked not to start a family if they are to get a job in the private sector. In other cases, maternity leave intervals were not taken into consideration as periods of service in cases of promotion in the education sector. Discrimination has been also manifested through the reduction in pay and benefits during periods of maternity leave or sick leave in the light of oncoming pregnancy, although legislation is supposed to prevent discrimination of this sort in the public sector (Greek Ombudsman, 2012).

1.2 Gender representation in history of Greece

In the history of Greece, gender representation was heavily influenced by societal norms, which were rooted in patriarchal structures. Ancient Greek society was predominantly male dominated, and women's roles were generally confined to the household and family matters. Nevertheless, there were exceptions and variations across different regions and time periods in ancient Greek history. For instance, Spartan women had more freedom and were involved in physical training and some public activities due to the unique social structure of Sparta. Generally, women's role in Greek society didn't change much until the end of 19th century, when feminist movements began.

As historical records mainly come from male authors, the perspective on women's roles in Greek society is limited and biased. While historical works on women and gender began to appear in the 19th century, it was not until the feminist movement of the 1970s and 1980s that a systematic analysis of gender practices and representations took place. These studies aimed to shed light on the experiences, struggles, and

achievements of women throughout history, with a particular emphasis on the women's movement. This turn to history allowed to show that the oppression of women is a social product and therefore can be challenged and reversed.

The 1980s at the same time witnessed the emergence of “new history” that was dealing with issues such as the extent of industrialization of Greece. This history paradigm prioritized the study of the state, economic and social development and social stratification, but gender appeared to be of secondary importance. The rise of this approach led to the marginalization of gender in Greek Universities, as it seemed to disrupt the “new historical narrative” that the state was trying to build after Greek Junta of 1967.

This situation seems to change only in the beginning of 2000s when more and more dissertations about gender are published in Greek Universities. Also, a lot of chapters dedicated to gender history have been appearing in general historical works. Greek Universities created post-graduate programmes about gender in an anthropological and historical approach (Papadogiannis, 2017. Avdela, 2010). Although a lot of academics support that gender still has a marginal position in greek history, some others claim that since the late 1990s there is “a dynamic process of diffusion of women’s and gender’s history in Greek historiographical production as a whole” (Fournaraki & Yannitsiotis, 2013).

1.3 Gender representation in history of Athens

Throughout the history of Athens, gender representation was deeply influenced by patriarchal norms and the general perception of the country throughout times, about confining women in domestic roles and in raising children. While there were some variations in different time periods, certain general patterns can be observed regarding the roles and status of women in Athenian society.

For example, in ancient Athens, women were excluded from participating in politics and holding public office. However, we meet various Greek goddesses with exceptional power and attributes like Athena, Hera and Artemis. In modern Athens, we meet remarkable women mostly as partners of powerful men in politics, science, and trade and less as individuals who contributed to Athenian society. Generally, women in Greece acquired the right to vote and being voted in the elections of 1954.

2. Female footprint in Athens

Despite these prevailing gender norms in Athens throughout its history, there were instances of women who held exceptional roles or gained influence through familial connections or other means. Throughout history and a lot of fights and sacrifices a lot of women left their mark in Greek society for their work and contribution in different aspects like art, science, culture, revolution and human rights.

Focus groups and research brought to surface a lot and different women throughout Greek history and their importance. Nevertheless, because of the limitation of the existence of a kind of monument, there were chosen to be presented Greek women (some known, some unknown), that monuments of them can be found in Athens. Let's present them.

2.1 Sappho, the lyric poet

Sappho (630-570 BC) was a Greek lyric poet from Lesbos, particularly known from antiquity until today. She wrote love poems, hymns to the gods and epithalamia (wedding songs). Her poetry vibrated with spontaneity and intense emotions. She gathered around her beautiful young girls, from the aristocracy of the island and from other cities of Asia Minor, in order to teach them the arts of music and poetry. However, Sappho's relationship with her pupils was considered inappropriate because it had erotic dimensions. She was considered to be homosexual and that identification accompanies the poet to this day. In modern times, lesbian love has also been associated with her name. Besides the sculptures of her in Lesbos, there is a brass statue of her in Onassis Culture Foundation, in Athens.

2.2 Manto Mavrogenous, the Greek heroine of the 1821

Manto Mavrogenous (1796-1840) was a Greek heroine of the Greek War of Independence (1821), that contributed her fortune for the Hellenic cause. Her origin was from Mykonos, where she led the rebellion of the island's inhabitants against the Turks. With ships, two equipped with her own money, she pursued the pirates who were ravaging the Cyclades and then fought in Pelion, Fthiotida and Livadia. Manto Mavrogenous' financial support of the Struggle and her general activities, such as her letters to the philhellenic women of France and England, made her name legendary in European philhellenic circles. For her overall contribution to the War, she was honoured by Ioannis Kapodistrias with the rank of Lieutenant General. She was persecuted and exiled by the politician Ioannis Kolettis and eventually died penniless in Paros, as she had spent her entire fortune on the struggle. Today you can find a bust of Manto Mavrogenous in Pedion tou Areos, Athens.

2.3 Katina Paxinou, the first non-American woman winning an Oscar

Katina Paxinou (1900 – 1973). She was the first Greek actress who managed to make it in Hollywood and even on her own terms, to excel in theatre and cinema in Europe and to stand out as a tragedienne of global importance. She was the first non-American actress that won an Academy Award for Best Actress for her performance in the film "For Whom the Bell Tolls". She played in numerous performances of the National Theatre of Greece. Her husband, the director Alexis Minotis, created a museum in her memory, that after his own death, was named Paxinos-Minotis Museum. The Museum and Archive are housed in the Eynardos Mansion, 20 Agios Konstantinos St. and 52 Menandrou Street, in the centre of Athens.

2.4 Antigoni Metaxa-Krontira, the creator of Greek Children's Theatre.

Antigoni Metaxa-Krontira (1905 – 1971) was an important Greek educator. She was the creator of the first children's theatre for children in Greece. She was the author of 54 children's books, including the six-volume children's encyclopedia and the Encyclopedia of Greek Mythology for children. She produced vinyl records of fairy tales and songs and the first children's television show. Her goal was to educate children by entertaining them. For all her work she was awarded by the Academy of Athens. After her death she is commemorated in the park opposite the maternity hospital "Elena Venizelos" on a marble plaque.

2.5 Opi Zouni, a female Greek artist

Opi Zouni (1941-2008). She was an important Greek painter and artist born in Kairo, with origin from Crete and Santorini. She studied in Greece, in School of Fine Arts. Due to her gender, she could not present her work in Greece. She has held over 70 solo exhibitions in Europe and 450 participations in group exhibitions. She was a representative of geometric art in Greece. Her creations were influenced by Arabic culture but also incorporated Greek elements. Unfortunately, in our country her work wasn't recognized at her time because she was a woman. Today, a lot of her paintings can be found in Greek National Gallery in Athens.

2.6 Roza Imvrioti, the pioneer teacher

Roza Imvrioti (1898-1977) was a Greek educator, a pioneer of special education, with a rich social and political activity. She worked as a teacher of literature in middle schools and in 1934 she became the first female middle school principal. She founded the first Experimental Special Primary School in Athens (1937), the first official effort in Greece for the systematic education of children with mental difficulties. Today, this school is still named by her name to pay tribute to her contribution and work in the field of special education and can be found in Kaisariani, Athens. She was an elected member of the Council of the International Women's Union. She was exiled and suffered tortures due to her political activity.

2.7 Lela Karagianni, the first Greek fighter against Second World War

Lela Karagianni (1898-1944) was a legendary fighter of the National Resistance against the German troops in the period 1941-1944. A protagonist of the «Secret War», although a mother of seven children, she was the first Greek citizen to offer organized resistance against the enemy. She created the organization named "Bouboulina", funded by herself. She was imprisoned (with her children) and executed by the Germans troops. She became a renowned symbol of resistance worldwide. After her death, she was awarded the Award for Virtue and Self-Sacrifice by the Academy of Athens and, in 2011, the honorary title of the Law of Nations by Yad Vashem, the Foundation for the Memory of Martyrs and Heroes (see Greek Lawyers of Nations), while in 2020 she was awarded the honorary rank of Brigadier General. Today, there is

a marble bust of her in Exarcheia square in Athens. Also, her house and base of her resistance movement in Plateia Amerikis is considered to be a historical monument that needs special protection.

2.8 Kalliroi Paren, the first Greek Feminist

Kalliroi Paren (1861-1940). She is considered to be one of the first Greek feminists. She also claims the title of the first Greek woman journalist, editor and director of the newspaper "Efimeris ton Kirion". It was written exclusively by women and addressed mainly to women in Athens and Piraeus. She had had a rich social and political activity, represented Greece in a lot of international conferences and was exiled for the political views. Through her own action, Greek government allowed to women to be able to study in the University. Today, a marble bust of her can be found in 1st cemetery of Athens.

2.9 Melina Mercouri, the Greek Ambassador

Melina Mercouri (1895-1967) as a charismatic personality was one of the most important Greek women of the 20th century. She was described as "the last Greek goddess" and "a woman of flame. She was distinguished as an actress, by playing in theatrical plays and movies that won international awards. She also left her mark as a politician with her fight against the dictatorship, but also with her interventions at international level as Minister of Culture. She initiated the fight for the return of Parthenon Marbles back in Greece, a fight that still continues. Today, there is a cultural foundation in her memorial that can be found in Polignotou 11, centre of Athens and a bust of her in Amalias Avenue and Dionysus Areopagitou in Plaka, Athens.

2.10 Tzeni Karezi, a talented actress

Tzeni Karezi (1932-1992) was an important Greek actress, with rich social and political activity. She came from a conservative family, that didn't allow her that job career. She went against her family wishes and managed to be a protagonist in important plays. During the Greek Junta in 1967-1974 was exiled for playing in a theatrical play with resistance messages. She was one of the most commercial and highest paid names in film and theatre. She died in 1992, due to cancer. Today, there is a theater "Tzeni Karezi", named by her name. Also in 1992 was created the foundation "Tzeni Karezi", that offers palliative care for free in cancer patients.

3. City's practices and local strategies in disseminating history patterns.

Greece and its capital Athens, has a rich history that dates back thousands of years and is accessible to all citizens up to today. Various archaeological sites and museums are located at the city center, such as Acropolis, the National Archaeological Museum, the Acropolis Museum etc. Also, the dissemination of history includes guided tours by experts- guides who provide insights into the significance and stories behind each

location. Very important are also the private and public cultural institutions like the Byzantine and Christian Museum and the Benaki Museum, that exhibit historical artifacts and artworks relevant to the city's history. Finally, there are various digital platforms in Greece and Athens, to disseminate historical information of different periods of time and geographical areas. Online archives, virtual tours, and interactive websites allow people from all over the world, to explore Greek and Athenian history.

Specifically, at a regional level, and according to the local history of each area in Greece, municipalities are organizing events and festivals to celebrate historical anniversaries, and the contributions or sacrifices of local people. However, women's contributions and perspectives have often been underrepresented in traditional historical narratives, so most of events and festivals don't include the gender perspective. When these celebrations are about women, are mostly dedicated to the tremendous sacrifices and fights of women, during the Greek War of Independence (1821) or the Second World War. It seems that despite the rich history of Greece and the variety of historical spots and museums, there is not an established and specific strategy for the promotion of equal gender representation in history. Most often the representation of women lays on the initiative of local institutions, organizations and stakeholders.

Despite this situation, a lot of steps have been taken recently to improve gender equality, something that is often being promoted through gender representation in history. Municipalities are obliged to have gender equality committees that act towards that direction. Recently, Municipality of Dirfya- Messapia in Evia took such a step by organizing an event dedicated to women that changed modern history with their work (<https://eviaportal.gr/pragmatopoiithike-ekdilosi-gynaikes-pou-echoun-allaksei-syghroni-istoria/>). Museums, historical sites, and cultural institutions in Greece have made efforts to include exhibitions and displays that highlight the contributions of women throughout history, in various fields, such as politics, art, science, and social movements.

4. First Focus Group with young People: Analyses and results

The deployment of the focus group activities with young people was designed in two groups, since we had received a big interest through registration forms. The 1st focus group of young people was organized face to face, on June 20, 2023, in Escape Athens venue. We had nine participations of young people between 14-18 years old, that were students at secondary school and high school. Five of them were female and four males.

The main findings are presented below.

4.1. Relevance with the field of History’.

It seems that most of the participants didn't have a lot of interaction with History. The majority had only related to history, through school lessons. However, as they indicated, the school lessons are not very appealing for them as they learn history with a stiff and non-attractive way, trying to memorize an information that they find of low relevance and use. Most of them, also mentioned that the information they receive in school is not enough and is repeated through their school years. Maybe history lessons, should include more information about history of other eras or other countries or other subjects.

However, participants seem to recognize the importance of history for humankind and society and refer to history as necessary to shape the future and avoid the mistakes of the past.

"It's not the history, it's the way they teach it. They force us to learn history, but if it was something we were interested in it would be much easier to learn" (Student, male, 14 years old).

" We could take from other stories, from other countries, not to put so much emphasis on the details and learn other information, other facts that will help us" (Student, male, 14 years old).

"History is essential for the smooth evolution of the human species. And I mean, if we don't have knowledge of the past, we can't know how to organize the future. It may sound a bit vague, but because there have been so many events, we have learned lessons through them, and by learning history, we know what we can avoid, what we can prefer, because through the experiences of people in history we evolve ourselves"(Student, male, 15 years old).

4.2. ‘Level of knowledge in history’.

All the participants reported important historical information, and some of them had also knowledge about gender equality history. Regarding their level of knowledge on male figures, the participants reported more than thirty male figures in Greek history, that were dominant throughout the times. Most of these figures, were heroes of the revolution against the Ottoman Empire or prime ministers of Greece the last two centuries.

"Under the Constitution of 1864, women still did not have the right to vote, only men over 21 had the right to vote. And we see how late it took for women to get the vote. That is, and what belongs to modern, recent history women didn't have it yet, which was also considered a liberal constitution." (Student, Male, 15 years old).

"I know many men from history, because they are actually dominant in history, from what we've learned at least; I know Heraclitus, Kapodistrias, Justinian and many others." (Female, Student, 16 years old).

"Kolokotronis, Miaoulis, all the heroes of the Revolution, Kapodistrias, Deligiannis, Kolletes, Venizelos..." (Female, Student, 16 years old).

The case was different regarding the knowledge of female figures, where it was more difficult to identify many of them. In that part and to support the participants, we provided different categories (science, arts, revolution, ancient Greece, sports, politics) and we asked them to think about a Greek female figure they know of the above-mentioned fields. However, they didn't manage to identify enough of Greek women in all categories. Here is a summary of the females identified:

- Science: Mari Kiouri, Margaret Sanger, Jane Addams
- Arts: Frida Kahlo,
- Revolution: Bouboulina, Manto Mavroggenous (heroes of the Greek Revolution of 1821), Roza Parks
- Ancient Greece: Hera, Afroditi, Athina (Olympian Goddesses)
- Sports: Anna Korakaki (recent Greek Olympian champion)
- Politics: Melina Merkoyri (actress and minister of culture), Maria Antouanetta,

Participants reported that the difficulty to identify Greek women in history exists probably because when a woman did something historically important, it was never reported just because of their gender. Young people supported that there were and still are stereotypes that women are lower, weak and need protection, something that needs to change because it is unfair, and we need to work towards gender equal world.

"I remember from politics Melina Mercouri trying to return the statues that had been stolen from Greece and asking for them back, but she didn't succeed in the end." (Student, Female, 16 years old).

"Back then they gave more credit to men, so even a woman who did something very historic, maybe they didn't even put her in the books and we don't even know her today because she was a woman" (Student, Male, 16 years old).

"I think it needs to change because a person cannot be determined by their genetic characteristics, i.e., they don't choose it, not skin color, not sexuality, not gender, not anything. A person should be distinguished by their acquired knowledge, by their education, by what they can accomplish, not by how they were born and what characteristics they have since then. That is why it must change, there should be no difference between men and women." (Student, Male, 15 years old).

4.3. 'Methods to promote women's footprint in history'.

Students reported that some information should be removed from history and be replaced and enriched with more important information for all genders. Moreover, to

develop and implement more interactive ways for learning history, because the goal is to learn and not just to memorize the information. Some recommendation they shared are the use of videos, quizzes, virtual games, that include information about women in history and can be used in school lessons.

Regarding the development of a transitional map, the participants imagined this to be divided with colours according to the historical era, someone is searching for. The map maybe should include not just texts of information, but also a video that presents the topic/woman that is spotted. Also, they suggested that this map should be more gamified, to provide more incentives for the young visitors. Moreover, it would be more interesting to them, if the visitor is able to add some information he/she may know about the spot or the historical woman and the potential to communicate with a history expert.

"Let's say that when we learn about a project/fact, we should not only take into account who performed that, but who thought of it as an idea, because it is certain that it will not only be men who thought of it, but there will also be women. " (Female, 16 years old.)

"There could be a quiz app, in an interactive way, that includes pictures, videos, so that the people using it learn better." (Student, Female, 16 years old).

"If you have a map, you could click on a point on the map and it would show you at that point that some projects have been done and it would have dates and it would show you some kind of video to see and then you could answer some questions based on the map" (Student, Female, 16 years old).

"So in these maps there should be a historian, a person, like when you send to some companies, let's say, in shops and you send them a message for help; so if you have a question, you don't have to sit down to look from various sources that they are not clear; you send the message, if you have a question, a gap or say some mistakes that are on the map or put your own knowledge, something that is not on the map." (Student, Male, 15 years old).

5. Second Focus Group with young people: analyses and results

This focus group was held online via Microsoft Teams, on June 30, 2023. A google form was created to manage the focus group participation and 8 young people from 18-25 years old expressed their interest to participate. All of them were women. However, some dropouts were noticed and the final focus group was realized with two members, reaching the target of 11 participants. These two participants were academic students in History-Archaeology Department, with an extensive interest in gender representation and women's empowerment.

For this focus group invitations were posted in social media and were sent in University Departments of Gender Studies, History, Social Psychology, Sociology and Human Studies.

The main findings are presented below:

5.1. 'Relevance with the field of History'.

Participants had a high level of relevance with history, as they were university history students. They refer to history as something essential to understand the past and shape the future. Participants refer to gender representation in history as something that we began to explore quite recently, despite the fact that they study history. That means that we must bring to surface all these gender matters.

"Is the contact you have with time and how that affects the future. Mostly I see these patterns happening and that's what fascinates me. But also, how we can ultimately be definitive in changing some things that were written into history and offer, help make changes" (Female, 21 years old).

"Because the issue of women is still in an early phase, at least in the part of history and how it is highlighted, there is still room to step in and highlight other things" (Female, 21 years old).

5.2. 'Level of knowledge in history'.

Both the participants had a high level of history knowledge, specializing in specific history eras, like Byzantine or Medieval era. Participants mentioned that they can think of numerous male figures in history, while it is more difficult to identify many female figures. However, both had a high knowledge about female figures in history, from different historical eras. They attribute this inequality of gender representation to the fact that history was written exclusively by men, but also to how society and families were organized.

a) Some female figures that were mentioned are:

Byzantine era: Irene of Athens

Venetian era: Women that claim the ducats, like Margarita, that claimed the ducat of Achaia, in Greece

Revolution of 1821: Manto Mavrogenous

Literature: Christiana Hildegard von Bingen (German), Tatiana Gritsi-Milliex, Alki Zei, Zorz Sarri

"Because I'm more into byzantine-medieval (history), I like it more, maybe that women had a legal protection more in Byzantium than in the medieval west and we see it because we have a lot of empresses (in Byzantium)" (Female, 22 years old)

"Especially now with the 100 years of Alki Zei and Zorz Sarri, I think it's a good example"
(Female, 22 years old)

"We're talking about a male-dominated space, at least that's what the history was, as it was projected, and then there's the fact of how they raised their families. I think it's very well known what I'm saying" (Female, 22 years old)

5.3. Methods to promote women's footprint in history'.

They stressed the importance of women representation in history in order to fight not just societal stereotypes, but also empower women to grow beside the established stereotypes. Despite the limited resources, the participants recommended that we should search for more historical resources and be more openminded towards the findings throughout history.

Some other recommendations are the enrichment of curriculums in History Departments, the creation of gender history departments in more Greek universities, and the development of seminars about gender equality in schools. They supported that education has a great role in shaping gender equality and when you add these elements in school lessons, that is when changes happen.

Moreover, the group highlighted the use of digital platforms, technology and social media are necessary, as participants support.

Regarding the development of transnational map, the participants imagined this should be divided in categories, depending on the footprint field by each woman. Also because of the rich work of women in history, the group suggested the creation of a platform where anyone can visit a museum virtually, and all the works made by women are highlighted.

"Empowerment is not only about the man, but also about the woman. That is, it has to be somehow a simultaneous work" (Female, 22 years old)

"When you want to dig deeper into a woman's story, you fall into the gap of resources. That's a gap we can't fill, because this is work that has already been done in the past. However, what we can certainly do is to dig deeper and be more openminded to what we find" (Female, 21 years old)

"To add courses to the already existing departments" (Female, 22 years old)

"I would say that we could do some seminars in universities or some schools; we could provide some additional information so that children from an early age who are starting out in the male-dominated space can see it and distinguish it" (Female, 22 years old)

"And then of course Instagram and how we could upload some videos or upload a picture and underneath a description referring to a link or a blog where we could write"
(Female, 22 years old)

"If it was about art, it could be in every museum or gallery, which works were made by women" (Female, 21 years old)

6. Focus Group with Stakeholders: Analyses and results

For the participation in the focus group a google form was created. It was held online via Microsoft Teams, on June 30, 2023. Twelve participants expressed their interest for participating. Finally, seven people participated. Five of them were female and two were male. The participant's profile was different. There were academics, educators, social workers working in university or in humanitarian sector.

Invitations were sent to universities, research centers, NGOs and in shelters of unaccompanied children. We considered important to have in this focus group also experts working with young people. The main findings are presented below.

6.1. 'Relevance with the field of History'.

Most of the participants had a high level of relevance with the field of History, as they were educators and academics. One participant was specialized in history and has deployed dedicated research to women of modern history. Two educators from the group had experience in projects with young people, focusing on gender equality through history.

"I recently finished my post-doctoral research, which was about the history of women, both living and non-living, from the interwar period to the present day, especially women who have survived torture. I focused mainly on the seven-year period, because that's where the bulk of the living women are, some are very well known, some not at all known, but that doesn't matter".

6.2. 'History through the lens of their expertise'

All participants shared that history is important as a topic, however the way it is taught from elementary school up to university, makes it very difficult to engage young people. They have highlighted the lack of new media and contemporary ways of teaching, and this creates a gap with how young people receive information and knowledge today. Moreover, regarding the content, some participants noted that we miss elements from the modern history after World War two, and for example historical moments after 1950s.

Furthermore, a very important finding was the acknowledgement from the participants, that history was written in a way that didn't include gender and for that reason also Greek language is focused in using male gender in written or oral discourse.

"The problems of gender in history begin with vocabulary. The discourse we use and the discourse in which our historical texts are written, in any case, does not have a gender dimension".

6.3. 'Experience with young people in the field of History'

Some of educators of the group had experience in working with young people in shelters of unaccompanied children. Although they didn't report their experience with teaching history, they mentioned their experience in interacting with young people about historical events and gender equality. They pointed out how important is for young people to learn about gender equality and how much they are interested in this topic, but also how difficult is for them to understand the elements of gender equality and how to implement in everyday life.

Participants highlighted the fact that young people have few knowledge about history in general and this becomes worst in historical achievements by female figures. Moreover, they mentioned the importance of technology in promoting history to young people, and specifically the use of social media and other interactive media.

"About history we refer to when we do an action or on the occasion of International Women's Day; various such actions, talking about equality, we also refer to female figures.

"If you talk about equality and discrimination, they will say we agree that we are all equal, women have the same rights as us. But in reality, in their everyday life you will see that this is not true."

"It is true that the young people do not seem to have good knowledge, neither qualitatively nor quantitatively, but the children are very interested and that is very important. I mean you see that when you tell them something, their interest in history is immediately revived".

"The beneficiaries show that they are ignorant, they don't know women figures of importance".

"I think now young people are attracted to social media and image. I think it's the image that they're more engaged with. So, I think that some videos that talk about such people but in an interesting way, maybe it would pique their curiosity and interest a little bit."

6.4. 'Women's footprint in History'

There is a great difficulty in the research of elements regarding women's footprint in history and specific information regarding female figures. However, some very important information was revealed during this focus group. One great example is the importance of the guerilla for the position of women during Second World War. Guerilla and the war placed women in a different situation, outside of home, having an

important role in espionage and in supporting their home in a different way when men were away.

Moreover, it was mentioned that even if in some areas there is a reference to a female figure, it is very difficult to find more information about this person and its achievements. Most of the times is only superficial reference and women are mentioned only as a name. The lack of extended knowledge regarding women that have gained high reputation, was commonly agreed.

"With a search I did to look for historical female figures, I found that there is very little reference to very little, at least in Larissa where I am, I found almost nothing in reference to a historical female figure who has left an era and is remembered".

"The women themselves reported that the guerrilla, for example, took them out of the house and gave them a place to stay. This is very, very important, that is, from where they did not exist, which were purely productive units in the home or in the fields, they gained a place in society, they took up positions that men could not carry out".

6.5. Suggestions from participants on female footprint in the city/in history.

Several female Greek figures in history in various fields were identified in this group, from various areas across Greece and mostly from the city of Athens. These are presented below:

- Diotima, Sappho (from ancient times)
- Aggeliki Panagiotatou (the first Greek female doctor, from the island of Kefallonia)
- Manto Mavrogenous, Bouboulina (from Greek War of Independence)
- Kalliroi Parren (the woman who started the feminist movement in Greece)
- Eleni Skoura (the first female member of the Parliament)
- Lina Tsaldari (the first female minister)
- Kaiti Tsarouxa, Xristina Moustakli (from Civil war and they are still alive)
- Lela Karagianni
- Kitti Arseni
- Melina Mercouri

One recommendation was to place a special focus in the recent years and especially the period after 1974, when trying to highlight the important female figures. This is a more recent history and can be more engaging to young people. Moreover, some women are still alive, and this might attract the interest of young people to learn more about these women and their achievement.

"So, the recent for us and the part that is incomplete in both books and teaching, is that we have all got up to 1974. We should be looking for women from 1974 to 2023".

7. Conclusions

1. Young people, under 18 years old, seem to have knowledge in history through school lessons, however, are not really engaged to the learning methods. Nevertheless, they seem to have knowledge in history through media, internet, and social media. This finding was also confirmed in the focus group of stakeholders, where it was reported that young people don't seem to have adequate historical knowledge, but they seem to have a big interest in learning more about history with more attractive and interactive ways. Young people over 18 old had a high level of knowledge in history, as they were university students in history department.
2. As far as it concerns gender representation in history, it seems that all members in the focus groups agreed that females are underrepresented in history, because history was written by males, and this reflects the power relations that existed for centuries in Greece up to today. That is why participants had difficulties in tracking down many female figures in history. This fact was also confirmed through the desk research, when as researchers, faced difficulties in finding many women that left their mark in Greek History or finding enough information about them.
3. A very interesting finding was the difficulty of the focus group with young people to recognize many Greek women that left their footprint in history. The majority of the women they recognized were not Greek. This reflects the way Greek history was written, but also how this history is being taught to the young people in school and universities. Many important women that we found through Desk Research were not mentioned by young people and are not even included in the Greek history lessons at school.
4. Gender equality in Greece, seems that still has a long way to go. Greece is a relatively new country developing in this area, comparing with other European countries. That may suggest that a lot of societal changes that happen to other European contexts, may need more time to be adopted by Greek society. Also, according to the European reports and research on traditional gender roles, it seems to be male dominant, being a constraint for many women that may want to evolve to different career paths, raise their children or follow different personal choices. Improvements were achieved the last decades, but economic crisis derailed a lot of these achievements. Changing the gender representation in Greek history can contribute a lot towards that direction.
5. The digital transnational map that is going to be created through HerStory project is something that excited all participants in the groups and we believe is going to be a very useful tool for promoting women's footprint and combating gender stereotypes. The digital form of this map is very attractive to young people who want to explore women's footprint in history. Academics also suggested the possibility of using it in history lessons, something that is going to raise the impact of the project.